

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

Bobomurodova Durdona Yusuf qizi

Science adviser: Shamuradova Naima Mukhtarovna

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Annotation: This article gives information the demanding and complex nature of English language teaching with young learners. The article begins with the challenges of the young learner classroom, then goes on to argue that the low estimation of teaching languages in primary education can seriously impact the confidence and efficacy of primary-school teachers. The popular myth that English for young learners is a simple matter requiring neither advanced language skills nor a deep knowledge of educational affordances and pedagogy is interrogated.

Key words: Teaching English to young learners; teacher education; creative teacher talk; children's literature;

It can sometimes be difficult getting your young learners to stay focused for an entire class. However, you can use that energy and curiosity to your full advantage. Here's how to teach English to children using engaging games and activities!

Once you've conquered getting TEFL certified, you can conquer anything, right? Not only is teaching children a particular challenge, but they are also usually complete beginners in their English learning journey.

This combination means that you'll have to pay particular attention to the way you present information and engage students. Engagement and fun is key to setting a strong foundation for their future education.

1. Turn lessons into songs

Every English learner, both native and not, is familiar with, at the very least, one classic jingle. Yes, the ABCs are what we turn to for a reminder of what letter comes after Q. Although the middle part (something about eliemenopee?) requires a bit more brain power, the song offers English speakers a comfortable reference point for all their alphabetical needs.

2. Create visual diagrams to illustrate new vocabulary

Use color and visual aids to keep kids' attention longer. Head, shoulders, knees, and toes. These are a whole lot easier to point out on a smiling stick man than to write out in a vocabulary list. Visual devices provide a double whammy, too. Students can enjoy coloring or even adding on to pictures, while also absorbing what the new words they are learning look like.

Highlighting, underlining, and circling are all common visual tricks adults use to recall snippets of information. Creating visual diagrams is the same basic idea, so that the little ones can start to visualize what English looks like. As a bonus, students can more easily locate learning aids with distinct colors and illustrations among their folders of messy papers.

3. Encourage mnemonic devices to memorize grammar rules

Please Excuse My Dear Aunt Sally, or PEMDAS, is a popular mnemonic device for recalling the order of operations in math. When it comes to teaching English to children, memory aids make it easier to remember hard-to-spell words or complex grammar points. Whether that

means creating a mnemonic device in students' native languages or breaking it down into simpler English words, the goal remains the same: better memory!

4. Weave in spontaneous or consistent dialogues throughout the lesson

What did you do this weekend? By kicking off class with an expected question, you can get your students thinking about what they'll say long before class even starts. Natural dialogue also introduces students to everyday vocabulary relevant to their own lives and interests.

5. Break up solitary study sessions with games

Ah, the holy grail of how to teach English to young learners — games.

Childhood education without games is like chicken wings without seasoning or sauce. You simply can't have one without the other. Games are especially effective teaching methods for young learners (or for any kind of learner — think back to your own TEFL certification program!), because kids are able to learn without realizing it. Active games let them expel some bottled up energy and quiet ones challenge and require concentration.

What are some games to try? Think of some you played as a kid!

- Hangman
- Memory game with card pairs
- 20 Questions
- I Spy
- Simon Says
- Charades

6. Review vocabulary through role playing

The best teaching methods for young learners require creativity.

Think theater class with an English twist. Picking up the role of a police officer or elderly neighbor on the spot can be intimidating to any aged student. However, if you have some fun with it and create a more relaxed expectation for students to act out roles, they'll be less stressed about making mistakes.

7. Repeat previous lessons in every class

Assuming the average class duration is only an hour or less, that leaves a whole lot of time in the day to forget everything a student just learned. Children won't retain as much information as adults, so repetition is key in English for young learners.

Rather than calling case closed at the end of a lesson and moving on after a test, be sure to pack every class with tons of repetition from lessons before. This also helps students to use vocabulary and grammar points all together, rather than depend on the same example sentences and templates they learn isolated in each lesson.

8. Get out of the classroom!

If you're a first-time English teacher, the idea of leading kids out into the big, wide world and outside the safe classroom walls may sound like a disaster waiting to happen. But if you're teaching English to young learners in-person and have permission to do so, take the kiddos out on a stroll. The change in scenery opens up a whole new box of situations to practice new vocabulary in its natural habitat.

In order for younger students to learn in a new environment, certain procedures and routines have to be established. Students must feel comfortable and welcome in their

learning environment. Young learners must be taught how to operate in a group classroom setting. For some, this is the first time as a student in a class of many. Students must learn to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and needs to both their peers and the adults they interact with at school. Students need to understand their role in the class and the teacher's role. So, what is a young learner's role? In my classroom, I teach students that they are writers. They are readers. They are scientists. They are explorers. Though many of them are learning to do these things for the first time, I want them to feel empowered to take risks in these endeavors. I want them to know that the skills they come in with, perhaps creating an illustration rather than writing a story, or interpreting the pictures in a book rather than reading the words, are valuable, too. It's important to me that they do not see themselves as being at a deficit when they enter my classroom. We work together to build upon skills that many of them have already.

A large part of early education also has to do with character education. Young learners are psychologically still very egocentric. Their world consists of themselves and everything that happens to them. Early educators teach these children to broaden this view, learning to care not only about what happens to them, but also what happens to the people around them. This is why we see the theme of community prevalent in many of the primary years. This is developmentally difficult for some young learners to understand. Early educators teach these learners about the community around them and how they are a part of this community. We teach young learners how to empathize with people who are both similar to and different from themselves. Empathy is a crucial behavior in becoming part of both their classroom community and the larger community in which they live. Once young learners have established themselves as part of a classroom community, the possibilities are endless. Young learners are exciting! When they become empowered to take risks, my students show amazing creativity. They are eager to contribute their ideas and are learning to value the ideas of their classmates. With the heavy emphasis on standards and achievement, some educators ask if learning starts too early. I say "No!" Learning can happen as long as a young learner's environment nurtures certain skills.

In order for young learners to thrive they must be taught

1. **Independence.** Young learners sometimes need prompting and support, but we have to believe in their ability to complete tasks on their own. There must be a gradual release of responsibility in every part of the day for student-centered learning to occur.
2. **Collaboration.** In my class, students frequently work in pairs or small groups. It is crucial that they know how to have their voices heard in these situations and how to support the learning of their peers. I want my students to be able to work together with an end goal in mind.
3. **Ownership.** Ownership of ideas and products acts as intrinsic motivation to put forth their best effort every time.
4. **Persistence.** In independent and collaborative work, young learners learn to try and continue trying even if they don't feel 100 percent confident. We have to encourage them to take risks!

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